

The Quality of Working Life and the Organizational Commitment of Municipal Employee in Samut Sakhon Province

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Abstract—This research aims to investigate: (1) Relationship between the quality of working life and organizational commitment of municipal employee in Samut Sakhon Province. (2) To compare the quality of working life and the organizational commitment of municipal employee in Samut Sakhon Province by the gender, age, education, official experience, position, division, and income. This study is a quantitative research; data was collected by questionnaires distributed to the municipal employee in Samut Sakhon province for 241 sample by stratified random sampling. Data was analyzed by descriptive statistic including percentage, mean, standard deviation and inferential statistic including t-test, F-test and Pearson correlation for hypothesis testing. Finding showed that the quality of working life and the organizational commitment of municipal Employee in Samut Sakhon province in terms of compensation and fair has a positive correlation ($r = 0.673$) and the comparison of the quality of working life and organizational commitment of municipal employees in Samut Sakhon province by gender. We found that the overall difference was statistically significant at the 0.05 level and we also found stability and progress in career path and the characteristics are beneficial to society has a difference was statistically significant at the 0.01 level, and the participation and social acceptance has a difference was statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

Keywords—Quality of working life, organizational commitment, municipal employee, Samut Sakhon province.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE external environment is changing rapidly; many highly competitive organizations must ready for the competition. The factors that are important priorities and serve as the core strengths of the organization is "Human resources," many organizations adopt a strategy for human resources management at the difference to attract quality people knowledge, skills, and culture, working toward the same goals with the organization to work together [2].

When the time comes, it will have to find ways to treat people well. These people are living longer with the organization, which was originally present to treat people well. It is common knowledge that those who stay with the organization for a long time must have ties with organizations and give organizational loyalty. Only the ties of loyalty and satisfaction with the organization make the employee stay longer. It is not enough for the most effective organizations to give employees a firm patriotic tie in the organization to keep

employees on the organization for a long time. Employees will work well and make a productivity and efficiency to the organization by the full capacity, which the organization will realize and become aware of their employee's ties to the organization and also find ways to strengthen the employee's ties [10].

The nature and authority of the municipal administration will be subject to common standards of personnel management and to a set of municipal administration that would allow the administration to develop the country [1]. This will enable departments to have a good morale. The loyalty of the municipal authorities as noted by the development of people and society to reflect changes in quality. This will also provide the solutions to strengthen the security of life and quality of working life of employees [3].

The quality of working life is happiness and satisfaction in the personnel working of the organization. The quality of working life is an important variable the affecting the productivity and profitability of businesses by the current focus on the factors and conditions that contribute to the quality of working life. The quality of working life with the fundamentals of living conditions there are elements which determine the quality of working life contributing to the operation and the feeling of satisfaction in the work and morale of workers [2].

The factors are causing the performance of personnel (is a link with the Quality of life or life quality of people's lifestyle features that are in line with the basic needs that are essential to human life and value.

Municipal officials are important in driving the municipal or local government agencies because they have to operate for the purposes of establishing local government and the principles of decentralized governance. There is a need to provide public services to meet the needs of local citizens by using the GPU [4].

The mission of the council is responsible the welfare of the people truly care about the people's quality of life better in every way. The mission functions such people in the organization need to work hard to achieve the objectives and goals of the organization. What the job will succeed depends on the sense of responsibility, sacrifice, dedication, physical support, solidarity and readiness of personnel in the organization is important. This stuff will happen voluntarily and feel loyalty and commitment towards the organization if the absence of these factors. Staff may have to migrate, quit, or change jobs or not; it was not practical. This cause will

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damage the organization and may affect the success of the participating organizations and may also affect the public by the end. In the conditions of today's world where the private sector has a high growth industry with increased investment, more personnel including the value of changes in personnel is needed, and most of the popular ones will not make graduates entering government. This was caused by higher returns of welfare or other benefits of those that are better than that [5].

The officials have a good quality of working life and a high commitment to the organization so not only is good for civil servants only but also the effect on the lives of the people involved. The importance of this research to drive a municipality or local government agencies can operate according to the principles of decentralized governance.

This study will aim to understand the quality of working life and the commitment of municipal employees to the organization and how that compares the quality of working life by personal factors. The results of this research will directly benefit the employees and executives of local councils or local governments. This information will be promoting development and improving the quality of life in the work of municipal employees. In the province of Samut Sakhon and can lead to the development of personnel management to be consistent with previous workload [3].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *The Concept of Quality of Working Life*

The concept of quality of life in scientific research has spread 30 to 40 years ago, when public welfare was explored more thoroughly while trying to understand the interface between the new public needs and economic development. Western welfare ideals of the second half of the twentieth century stimulated rapid economic growth. However, an increasing number of material goods was accompanied by contradictory consequences [6].

U.S. President Lyndon B. Johnson seems to have been the first person to refer to the concept of quality of life, in 1964. In 1972 Johnson detailed the concept, saying that more important than the number of goods available to Americans is their impact on their quality of life. The trends of the society development clearly testified that the mere capital growth is not enough for public prosperity. This feature of economic progress is noted as Easterlin paradox: (1) richer people are happier than those living in poverty, (2) citizens of the richest countries in the world are not happier than they were a few decades ago, although they are significantly enriched by economic growth over the period. The changes in Lithuania's gross domestic product (GDP) and citizen satisfaction with life may be an illustration of the second part of Easterlin findings [7].

Although subsequent studies using more happiness indicators showed that in developed countries income growth has expanded the "happy life years" at the same time, it has been noticed that there is a certain threshold when personal income become much higher than the national average income. If this threshold is crossed, life satisfaction is less

dependent on further income growth. When the income is sufficient for normal daily life, and other factors that promote personal development and change of values growing favorably, new horizons of human needs or levels of the so-called "Maslow" hierarchy of needs) begin to widen. This is related to the needs of communication, recognition, and self-realization, the fulfilment of which is the most important factor for a full-fledged human well-being and happiness [6].

The quality of life and happiness is the subject of humanities, social sciences, and biomedicine. Researchers choose the methods for measuring the quality of life depending not only on the research area but also on the number of dimensions, on their objective or subjective nature, on the influence of culture and values. Sociologists and political scientists are more interested in the quality of life on a society-wide level, while psychologists and biomedical representatives delve into individual, subjectively perceived the quality of life and happiness. For example, the World Health Organisation defines Quality of Life as individuals' perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns. In this regard, it is a broad ranging concept affected in a complex way by the person's physical health, psychological state, the level of independence, social relationships, personal beliefs and their relationship to salient features of their environment has presented a table, to sum up the findings of happiness from different research fields [8].

From the management perspective, the relationship between happiness and creative productivity is considered an important aspect of a successful business reasons. It is recognized that investing in the quality of life at work can bring great benefits to both individuals and the organisation as a whole. This approach is increasingly gaining ground in practice – more and more organisations implement employee motivation measures to promote healthy working relationships and commitment to the mission, which is in line with ideals of a society, the perception of their role and responsibility in the organisation, the need to improve professional competence and the desire to realise personal potential. The results of such policies can be seen as an arising double (employee happiness, and the organization's efficiency) spiral [9].

B. *Conceptualization of Organizational Commitment*

Organizational commitment has been conceptualized and defined in different ways some researchers regard organizational commitment as a uni-dimensional construct. Kanter viewed commitment as the willingness of social actors to give energy and loyalty to the organization. According to Porter, commitment involves willingness of employees to exert higher efforts on behalf of the organization, a strong desire to stay in the organization, and willingness to accept major goals and values of the organization. Most of the researchers in this field regard organizational commitment as a multidimensional construct. Nowadays, Porter and Steers classified commitment as attitudinal commitment and behavioral commitment. Attitudinal commitment refers to an

individual's identification with the organizational goals and willingness to work toward them. In behavioral commitment, employees are viewed as committed to particular organizational behaviors rather than to an entity [7] and classified commitment into three forms; compliance, identification, and internalization. And they identified more than 25 ways in which organizational commitment was conceptualized and measured and identified three general themes that characterized various approaches to the conceptualizations of organization commitment, namely, affective attachment to the organization, perceived costs associated with leaving the organization, and a moral obligation to remain with the organization. Employees with effective commitment undertake actions because they want to; employees with continuance commitment engage in actions because they need to in order to avoid the cost of leaving the organization, and employees with normative commitment engage in actions because they should [8]. These three forms of commitment interact and employees can experience all the three forms in varying proportions. Based on the review of various definitions of commitment, it does appear that there is some general consensus that commitment is a force that binds an individual to the organization. It is seen as an individual's psychological attachment to an organization or a psychological bond that connects an individual to his/her organization [11]. Table I outlines the ways in which organizational commitment has been defined in the literature.

TABLE I
NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES IN 11 MUNICIPALITIES IN THE PROVINCE OF SAMUT SAKHON AND SAMPLES

Small municipalities	Answerer	
	Population (N)	The sample (n)
1. Sakhon Nakhon	207	82
2. Autonomous District	27	11
3. The main five parish councils	19	7
4. District Nadi	29	12
5. Ya Phraek District	24	9
6. Municipality Om	113	45
7. Baen Municipality	65	26
8. Municipal Park	34	14
9. District Agriculture Development	29	11
10. Autonomous District	22	9
11. The main five parish councils	39	15
Sum	608	241

The organizational commitment is the condition of the individual to be associated with their actions or certain behaviors. It is also a willingness to follow the rules of the organization [11].

III. METHODOLOGY

This research has given the demographics and the sample.

1. The population in this study is that municipal employees in the province of Samut Sakhon. A total of 11 municipalities, including the city of Samut Sakhon. Ban Bang Pla Mr. Bal Tech District, China Nadi District Ya Phraek District Om municipality Baen Municipality Suan

Luang District District Agriculture Development Autonomous District Councils and District Five The number of employees totaled 608 [10].

2. The sample used in this study generate by the formula of population Yamane (Yamane) to calculate the sample size, and using the 95 percent confidence level and percentage tolerances 5 ($\alpha = 0.05$) had a sample size of 241 people by means of random sampling session landscape by strategical random sampling [4].

A. Data Collection

The researcher collected data by asking for a letter of recommendation from the faculty of management since and cooperation with the local municipal employee in Samut Sakhon province questionnaires to a sample of 241 respondents.

1. Analyze and describe the personal information of municipal employees will using descriptive statistics (Descriptive Statistics) include frequency and percentage [6].
2. Analyze data about the comments on the job. Environment and opinions demonstrate a commitment to the organization as mean and standard deviation by the scores and divide the review into five levels to find the width of the class interval [3].

IV. FINDINGS

The quality of working life for Samutsakorn municipal employees and are moderate in descending order, the descending below the characteristics that are beneficial to society follow by a stability of work, social acceptance, fairness in the evaluation performance, and safety and quality adequate and fair compensation.

Adequate and fair compensation, the quality of working life for municipal employees for the overall moderate have been observed. The sort of item that has the highest average first three are very pleased with the extra (bonus) that the agency is a minor satisfaction with benefits received from the agency provided to the family and satisfaction with benefits received by the agency in order to get the lowest average salary is enough to pay each month [3].

1. Safe and healthy working conditions the overall moderate the sort of item has the highest average three top three are workplaces have sufficient lighting for the performance, physically and mentally with the atmosphere and determine regulatory job description in working to prevent accidents strictly respectively. The lowest average in the workplace is noisy cause will affect to the performance [5].
2. Development of the municipal employees of Samutsakorn that effect to the quality of working life. The overall moderate the sort of item that has the highest average three top three priority to the development of knowledge and ability. The first minor was encouraged to further their education by scholarship, and the opportunity to be able to work fully, respectively, while the lowest factor is a presentation is a financial beneficial [6].

3. Participation and social acceptance of the quality of working life for Samutsakorn municipal employees. The overall level the sort of item that has the highest average 3 factors. The first is work colleagues have good relations with each other. A minor problem when in operation get help from colleagues as a team and supervisors will have the opportunity to participate in the review of the work by the lowest average gain recognition and respect for the skilled worker from supervisors [7].
 4. Fairness in the performance of the quality of working life for Samutsakorn municipal employees. The overall moderate the sort of item that has the highest average top three are commanders, including the opportunity to work with full knowledge. The second is the freedom to work fully and can make decisions about work assignments from supervisors on their own, respectively, the lowest ever to be trained in ethics in practice [8].
 5. The balance of work life and personal life for Samutsakorn municipal employees. The overall moderate sort by item, with an average top 3 include satisfaction with the holiday time at the agency designated, and a minor can break time at work and more time with your family properly.
 6. The job is useful to society effect to the quality of working life for Samutsakorn municipal employees. The overall level. The sort of item that has the highest average three top three factors have participated in the work day by tradition or national events and to assist local people working directly is the lowest average ever participated in blood donation to the hospital [9].
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V. DISCUSSION

Research on quality of working life and commitment to the organization of Samutsakorn municipal employees has been done. The researchers found the key issues to be discussed as follows.

The quality of life results from the work of Samutsakorn municipal employees. It concluded that Samutsakorn municipal employees with the quality of working life for Samutsakorn municipal employees. This shows that the bosses or managers that are involved with the operation of Samutsakorn municipal employees to take to improve development and the administration effectively meet the needs of Samutsakorn municipal employees more [2].

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